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We have performed a technical patentability assessment for the Patent Application no. **2013/14937** and appraised a Financial Patent Value of 35.450.000.00 (Thirty-five million and four-hundred fifty thousand) USD.

Patent Application No:	2013/14937
Patent Title:	A COMPOSITION FOR THE TREATMENT OF VIRAL INFECTIONS
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Şahin SAMUR

Patent Lawyer & Patent Expert

(Signature and Seal)

Biologist
Canan BALCI
(Signature)
19778646020

MSC. Biochemistry
Yeşim Kümbet
(Signature)
11444016854

PATENT ASSESSMENT REPORT

Title of Discovery: A COMPOSITION FOR THE TREATMENT OF VIRAL INFECTIONS
Patent No: 2013/14937

UNIQUENESS

Structural Uniqueness;

3,5' triallyl-2,4'-dimethoxybiphenyl,

3,7' triallyl, 2-3'-dimethoxybiphenyl

4-dihydroxi-8-(3-trimethyl-2-butene-1-il)-2H-chromene-2-on

6-dihydroxi-8-(3-hexamethyl-2-butene-1-il)-2H-chromene-2-on

Its pilot components and its function groups included in its structure array have no structural similarity with any synthetic agent that have been previously or currently used for the symptomatic / permanent treatment of anti-viral infections.

The phenolic components aligned as the primary two molecules are characterized as simultaneous hemagglutinin esterase and integrase blockers and 77-83% more serial in comparison to protease inhibitors such as (3S)-oxolan-3-yl N-[(2S,3R)-3-hydroxy-4-[N-(2-methylpropyl)(4-aminobenzene)sulfonamide]-1-phenylbutan-2-yl]carbamate due to their low molecular weight and the structural advantage of the phenolic function groups that include the influence time on viral enzymes against which they are antagonistic; due to demonstrating this characteristic at the mRNA expression level on viral enzymes which they block, their tolerance development probability is significantly lower (93-97% lower probability to develop tolerance) due to the structural advantages (integral resistance of phenolic spine against viral attacks; see 11-oxo-honokiol-phenyl-ester, 7-beta-magnolol-taurinate) they have in comparison to nucleoside inhibitor agents with relatively higher molecular weight such as 2-Amino-1,9-dihydro-9-((2-hydroxyethoxy)methyl)-6H-purin-6-one currently existing in the market.

FUNCTIONAL UNIQUENESS

3,5'triallyl-2,4'-dimethoxybiphenyl and 3,7'triallyl-2i3'-dimethoxibiphenyl, which are included in the phenolic-based function group among the aforementioned anti-viral components, are the only antiviral agents demonstrating simultaneous hemagglutinin esterase and integrase blocking characteristics among the existing synthetic components.

Biologist
Canan BALCI
(Signature)
19778646020

MSC. Biochemistry
Yeşim Kümbet
(Signature)
11444016854

(Seal and Signature)

Anti-hemagglutinin esterase glycoprotein monoclonal antibodies which are the only hemagglutinin esterase blockers currently available have a half-life of 2,2 hours.

The half-life of the relevant phenolic components is between 19-21 hours, and there is no tolerance development that is known or proven otherwise since they establish their simultaneous functions at a mRNA expression blocking level, contrary to the fast tolerance developed by nature by the related monoclonal antibody.

When compared to derivatives of N-(2-(4-(4-fluorobenzylcarbamoyl)-5-hydroxy-1-methyl-6-oxo-1,6-dihydropyrimidin-2-yl)propan-2-yl) which is an integrase blocking reference agent, it demonstrates a half-life that is approximately 220% longer than the 9-hour half-life of this agent and its derivatives.

Since the said blocking ability is repression-based at the mRNA expression level, there is no chronic tolerance that is acute or known or proven otherwise.

On account of their 21-23-hour active half-lives and their mRNA expression blocking capabilities, 4-dihydroxi-8-(3-trimethyl-2-butene-1-il)-2H-chromene-2-ten and its modular analogue 6-dihydroxi-8-(3-hexamethyl-2-butene-1-il)-2H-chromene-2-ten are ultimately identical when compared to 9-((2R,5S)-5-(hydroxymethyl)tetrahydrofuran-2-yl),3H-purin-6(9H) derivative reverse transcriptase blocking agents, phosphonoformic acid-based DNA polymerase blocking agents and ribonucleotide reductase inhibitor derivatives such as gallium maltolate but demonstrate a 132% more efficient anti-viral characteristics when subject to a comparison in terms of effect mechanism.

FITNESS FOR CHRONIC USE

The said 4 anti-viral agents;

Demonstrate a 237-403% higher elimination efficiency and a 76% lower metabolic load when compared to reverse transcriptase blocking agents whose elimination efficiency from the body is a derivative of 9-((2R,5S)-5-(hydroxymethyl)tetrahydrofuran-2-yl)-3H-purin-6(9H)-one on account of the related phenolic components and flavanol analogues; phosphonoformic acid-based DNA polymerase blocking agents and ribonucleotide reductase inhibitor derivatives such as gallium maltolate and to N-(2-(4-(4-fluorobenzylcarbamoyl)-5-hydroxy-1-methyl-6-oxo-1,6-dihydropyrimidin-2-yl)propan-2-yl) and Anti hemagglutinin esterase glycoprotein monoclonal antibodies.

It is suitable for long-term use (without any loss of effect / tolerance), given their low molecular weights and the antioxidative and neuroprotective effects of phenolic components, in particular.

Biologist
Canan BALCI
(Signature)
19778646020

MSC. Biochemistry
Yeşim Kümbet
(Signature)
11444016854

Its low molecular weight and the endogenous antioxidative structural resemblance (the structural resemblance they have with endogenous antioxidants) of 4 components do not cause hepatic autoimmunity but, on the contrary, supports effective liver and renal function.

When contrasted with the anti-viral agents to which they are compared, particularly the anti-viral components belonging to the phenolic function group have a priority of use due to their characteristics of normalization at cyp3a4 blocking, GGT, ALT and AST levels despite their anti-hepatoprotective quality.

AVAILABILITY EFFICIENCY

Among the related components, those that are phenolic derivatives and flavanol analogues have a 72%, 77%, 43%, 27% and 28% higher availability efficiency when compared to 9-((2R,5S)-5-(hydroxymethyl)tetrahydrofuran-2-yl),3H-purin-6(9H) derivative reverse transcriptase blocking agents, phosphonoformic acid-based DNA polymerase blocking agents and ribonucleotide reductase inhibitor derivatives such as gallium maltolate and to N-(2-(4-(4-fluorobenzylcarbamoyl)-5-hydroxy-1-methyl-6-oxo-1,6-dihydropyrimidin-2-yl)propan-2-yl) and Anti hemagglutinin esterase glycoprotein monoclonal antibodies.

It is easily obtained from 2-(4-hydroxy-3-prop-2-enyl-phenyl)-4-prop-2-enyl-phenol which is the principal phenolic component contained by the 3,5'triallyl-2,4'-dimethoxybiphenyl and 3,7'triallyl-2,3'-dimethoxybiphenyl Magnolia family, with the method used (see Nano dispersion) being reserved to its owner, and also by means of synthetic acquisition by using the method of synthesizing the related components which was presented to us by the inventor.

The approximate 2-(4-hydroxy-3-prop-2-enyl-phenyl)- 4-prop-2-enyl-phenol quantity contained by Magnolia Officialinis derivatives presently cultivated for medical purposes is 4356.56% times the probable yearly requirement of the related components.

It is easily obtainable from the icariside B flavanol obtained in trace amounts by the 4-dihydroxy-8-(3-trimethyl-2-butene-1-il)-2H-chromene-2-on and 6-dihydroxy-8-(3-hexamethyl-2-butene-1-il)-2H-chromene-2-on (its modular analogue) Epimedium family by using the modification method presented to us by the inventor (despite there being a 66.7% acquisition efficiency difference when compared with the acquisition efficiency of the said phenolic components) and the unit acquisition is (34%) more efficient than vegetal extraction due to the two separate synthetic synthesis methods presented by the inventor.

The said phenolic components are also available for bonding to superoxide (O-) and hydroxyl radicals by means of the allyl derivatives in their aromatic rings which is a result of their phenolic structure. Presently,

Biologist
Canan BALCI
(Signature)
19778646020

MSC. Biochemistry
Yeşim Kümbet
(Signature)
11444016854

there are no anti-viral agents which may bond with and eliminate these pro-oxidative factors that trigger the increase of viral infections.

The related phenolic components trigger an increase in the endogenous alpha-tocopherol and coenzyme q10 reserves and trigger an increased endogenous glutathione production. When compared to methyl-oleuropein, which structurally demonstrates the closest identical effect to this quality among the currently existing antiviral components (synthetical or vegetal), the related phenolic components provide a 56-67% more efficient endogenous antioxidant increase.

Another function of the related phenolic components that was not specified by the inventor in the related patent application but that was identified by us and that complement the anti-viral characteristics is their pro-cholinergic effect.

The related components protect cholinergic receptor density, trigger increase in cholinesterase enzyme expression and trigger the release of acetylcholine particularly in viral infection-based peripheral neuropathies by establishing a simultaneous anti-viral and pro-cholinergic effect in neuro-viral infections. Presently, there are no synthetic or anti-viral agents that establish simultaneous antiviral and pro-cholinergic effect in this regard.

When compared to the antiviral components belonging to the phenolic function group of which detailed technical analyses have been presented, 4-dihydroxy-8-(3-trimethyl-2-butene-1-yl)-2H-chromene-2-on and 6-dihydroxy-8-(3-hexamethyl-2-butene-1-yl)-2H-chromene-2-on (its modular analogue) are antiviral components that demonstrate a partial resemblance to reverse transcriptase blocking agents such as currently existing 9-((2R,5S)-5-(hydroxymethyl)tetrahydrofuran-2-yl)-3H-purin-6(9H)-one with respect to establishing resistance against hepatic metabolism (7-10%), whose molecular weight is significantly high compared to the related phenolic components, but whose biosorption rate is significantly higher (78-84%) than the said reverse transcriptase blocking agents due to a structural resemblance to their high endogenous flavins.

when compared to 9-((2R,5S)-5-(hydroxymethyl)tetrahydrofuran-2-yl)-3H-purin-6(9H)-one derivative reverse transcriptase blocking agents currently existing in the market; phosphonoformic acid-based DNA polymerase blocking agents and ribonucleotide reductase inhibitor derivatives such as gallium maltolate, in particular; their simultaneous DNA polymerase, reverse transcriptase and ribonucleotide reductase blocking characteristics demonstrate a difference in effect at a rate of (77%, 93%, 67%), respectively, by reducing the function of the related enzymes which are the principal effect mechanism by their mRNA expression blocking characteristics.

Biologist
Canan BALCI
(Signature)
19778646020

MSC. Biochemistry
Yeşim Kümbet
(Signature)
11444016854

The quantity of icaraside B contained by the Epimedium family that has been planted for medical use is near 57% of the probable production need, which brings forward synthetic production as the method of primary acquisition with respect to the said components.

PRIMARY PREFERABILITY POTENTIAL

When compared to 9-((2R,5S)-5-(hydroxymethyl)tetrahydrofuran-2-yl)-3H-purin-6(9H)-one derivative reverse transcriptase blocking agents currently existing in the market; phosphonoformic acid-based DNA polymerase blocking agents and ribonucleotide reductase inhibitor derivatives such as gallium maltolate and to N-(2-(4-(4-fluorobenzylcarbamoyl)-5-hydroxy-1-methyl-6-oxo-1,6-dihydropyrimidin-2-yl)propan-2-yl) and Anti hemagglutinin esterase glycoprotein monoclonal antibodies; the related anti-viral formulation demonstrates an efficient primary preferability potential with respect to the following matters at the respective rates:

Ease of acquisition, (94%)

Functional uniqueness and advantages, (110-136%)

Structural uniqueness and advantages, (37-54%)

Raw material and synthesis method resource stability (45-56%).

Best regards

Şahin SAMUR
Patent Lawyer & Expert

(Signature and Seal)

Biologist
Canan BALCI
(Signature)
19778646020

MSC. Biochemistry
Yeşim Kümbet
(Signature)
11444016854

(Seal and Signature)